

GERB-HR-ED01 rlut 1hrCM

**TOA outgoing longwave radiation, monthly-mean diurnal cycle
resolving each day into 1-hour means**

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1. Intent of This Document and Point Of Contact

1a) This document is intended for users who wish to compare satellite derived observations with climate model output in the context of the CMIP/IPCC historical experiments. Users are not expected to be experts in satellite derived Earth system observational data. This document summarizes essential information needed for comparing this dataset to climate model output. References are provided at the end of this document to additional information.

This GERB dataset is provided as part of an activity to increase the usability of GERB satellite observational data for the modelling and model analysis communities. This is not currently a standard GERB satellite instrument product, but does represent an effort on behalf of the GERB project team to identify a product that is appropriate for routine model evaluation. The data may have been reprocessed, reformatted, or created solely for comparisons with climate model output.

Users of these data should ensure they reference Harries *et al.* (2005) in any presentations or publications.

Dataset File Name (as it appears on the ESGF):

rlut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-0_BE_gn_200701-200712.nc
rlut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-0_BE_gn_200801-200812.nc
rlut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-0_BE_gn_200901-200912.nc
rlut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-0_BE_gn_201001-201012.nc
rlut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-0_BE_gn_201101-201112.nc
rlut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-0_BE_gn_201201-201212.nc

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2. Data Field Description

CF variable name, CMIP short name, units:	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux, rlut, W m ⁻²
Spatial resolution:	1° × 1°
Temporal resolution and extent:	1hrCM (monthly-mean diurnal cycle resolving each day into 1-hour means), from 200705 to 201212
Coverage:	Area bound by 60°N/S by 60°E/W

3. Data Origin

The Geostationary Earth Radiation Budget (GERB, Harries *et al.* 2005), instruments operate on board the four Meteosat Second Generation (MSG, Schmetz *et al.* 2002) series of geostationary satellites. These satellites were subsequently renamed Meteosat-8 through to 11. The GERB instruments are broadband radiometers that make observations, approximately every 15 minutes, of the Earth's emitted longwave (~4.0 to 100 μm) radiation and reflected shortwave (~0.32 to 4 μm) radiation over

a geographical region roughly from 60°N to 60°S in latitude and 60°W to 60°E in longitude. Also onboard each of the Meteosat satellites is the Spinning Enhanced Visible and InfraRed Imager (SEVIRI) which provides observations of the reflected shortwave and emitted longwave radiances in narrow bands over the same nominal region but at a higher spatial resolution. Data from the SEVIRI instruments are used widely by the operational meteorological and research community and are employed in several steps in the GERB product processing.

The GERB emitted thermal radiances are derived from the GERB observations using information on the spectral properties of the scene derived from the SEVIRI narrow-band observations. Outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) fluxes are determined from these emitted thermal radiances based on regressions utilising the SEVIRI narrow band observations. These regressions have been determined from simulations of narrow band and broadband radiance and flux for a wide variety of scene types. Spatial information from the SEVIRI instrument is also used to correct for sub-footprint non uniformity in the GERB observations.

At present, only data from the GERB instrument onboard Meteosat-9 (GERB-1) have been processed for submission to the obs4MIPs archive covering the period from May 2007 until December 2012. However, during this period, owing to operational constraints of the GERB instrument, data are only available for six months of each year. These are the same for each year: January, May, June, July, November and December.

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the processing chain employed to generate the 1hrCM *rlut* product from the GERB level 2 HR OLR fluxes. There are three main stages. The first ingests the Edition 1 GERB HR OLR data and generates an area weighted flux product at 1° by 1° spatial resolution for every 15 minute time interval. In the second stage these data are averaged over time to produce an hourly averaged product. Each hour interval is defined as the time-centred mean at half-past the hour, e.g. 1030 UTC comprises of the mean of data from 1000 UTC, 1015 UTC, 1030 UTC and 1045 UTC (or from those slots in this window that are available). An hourly average is produced for a 1° by 1° grid cell if there is one or more observation from the four observation times available for that grid cell. The final processing stage averages the hourly mean fluxes over the days in the month to produce a one degree monthly mean product at hourly intervals. The number of data points (days per monthly hourly mean) contributing to each monthly mean are used to estimate the uncertainties associated with the product. This is discussed in more detail in section 4.

Figure 1: Summary of the processing steps employed to produce the GERB monthly hourly mean longwave flux at 1° x 1° (*rlut*).

An example of the GERB monthly hourly mean outgoing longwave flux at the TOA (*rlut*) product for June 2008, plotted from 00:30 to 23:30 at hourly intervals, is shown in figure 2. There are many notable features including the contrast between the diurnal cycles for the warmer daytime land surfaces (e.g.

northern Africa and the Arabian Peninsula), cooler but less variable in time, ocean surfaces, and high cloud tops.

Figure 2: Example of GERB *rlut* product for hourly monthly-mean intervals for June 2008, starting at 00:30 (top left), to 23:30 (bottom right), over the nominal geographical region from 60°N to 60°S by 60°W to 60°E.

4. Validation and Uncertainty Estimate

There are three main sources of error that have been considered which are the absolute accuracy of the GERB radiance measurement, the uncertainties in determining a flux from a radiance, and the impact of missing data on the average fluxes.

4.1 Absolute accuracy

Quoted bias errors for GERB emitted thermal radiances are 0.96% during the night and 1.08% during the day for a typical full scale radiance ($77 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ sr}^{-1}$). Radiance to flux scenes specific biases can introduce additional bias in the OLR fluxes for some scenes of 2.6%. A detailed description of the absolute accuracy of the GERB longwave radiance measurements is discussed in Russell (2017) which considers the impact of uncertainties in the geolocation of the measured radiances, and provides cautions with respect to aerosols and thin cloud contamination.

4.2 Radiance to flux uncertainties

GERB LW fluxes use theoretical radiance to flux conversions based on plane parallel simulations across a large variety of scenes. A regression analysis relates the observed SEVIRI thermal channel radiances to the associated flux, implicitly performing a scene identification. The concept behind this approach is described in Clerbaux *et al.*, 2003. The scatter about the best fit regression leads to a 2.3% (1 sigma) scene and angle dependent random error for the instantaneous products, but at the monthly hourly scale scene variability results in the residual effect being generally well below one percent. A further bias of up to 1.3% is possible due to the specified accuracy of the SEVIRI channel inter-calibration. In addition limitations in the radiance and flux simulations lead to high biases for hot desert scenes at low viewing zenith (the Sahara during the middle of the day) of a few percent and low biases of up to 5% at the very edge of the GERB valid field of view.

4.3 Impact of missing data

Even for the months not affected by observing operational constraints, there are often days with missing hours. This occurs for a variety of reasons and tends to be a relatively random with regards to timing. To assess the impact of such missing data on the quality of the monthly mean diurnal product, December 2012 data were used to investigate the effect on the LW product at the 1 degree scale of removing an increasing number of days before calculating the monthly hourly mean. Days removed were randomly selected, with 16 selection realizations used to assess the robustness of the results. The effects of removing blocks of successive days was also investigated for comparison.

Table 4.1 shows, for the December 2012 11:30UTC hourly average, the mean and standard deviation of the resulting error at the 1 degree scale due to one, two, three, four and five days of missing data. In all cases no significant overall bias is introduced, but the magnitude of the expected error at the 1 degree scales increases with the amount of missing data, as shown by the increase standard deviation from just over 1.0 Wm⁻² for one missing day to in excess of 2.5 Wm⁻² for five missing days. The results in the table are determined over all the different realisations of the missing data but the pattern of missing days can contribute to the expected error. This can be seen from figure 3 which shows the standard deviations for each individual realization as well as the impact of removing three consecutive days of data from the start, middle and end of the month. To maintain consistency with the shortwave products rlt products are not produced for hours where there are more than five missing days in the month. Even in the case of five missing days, errors in the rlt estimate at the 1 degree scale due to missing data are less than the errors expected from the radiance to flux conversion.

	LW flux uncertainty estimate (Wm ⁻²)				
Number of missing days	1	2	3	4	5
Mean difference	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.01
Standard deviation	1.07	1.54	1.94	2.27	2.55

Table 4.1: Summary of the mean difference between no missing days and up to five randomly removed (missing) days in the December 2012 hourly monthly mean centred at 1130 UTC. The standard deviation about the mean difference is also shown.

Figure 3: Impact on the standard deviation (σ) in the LW flux difference for an increasing number of missing days (N) within an hourly monthly mean (here shown for the December 2012 1130 UTC time-slot r). Also shown is the impact on the standard deviation of removing three consecutive days at the beginning, middle and end of the month.

Figure 4 provides an overview of the availability of the monthly hourly mean flux products from 2007 to 2012. The figure also highlights those recurring periods each year when data are not available owing to instrument operational constraints (areas in white), but also indicates unplanned periods when the amount of missing data precludes the provision of the product (red). For those periods when data are provided, the figure indicates the number of days in which data were missing; green: zero to three days and blue: four or five missing days.

Figure 4: Summary of the periods when GERB-1 Edition 1 data are available to produce the *rlut 1hrCM* products from 2007 to 2012. Data are available for those periods indicated in green (up to three missing days per hourly monthly mean) and blue (four or five missing days). Those periods in the record where data have not been produced are shown in white and red. White indicate insufficient data owing to GERB instrument operational constraints, and red indicates insufficient numbers of observations for other reasons (e.g. unplanned data outages).

5. Considerations for Model-Observation Comparisons

The GERB instrument is geostationary and has a fixed viewing geometry. This means that angle specific biases in the radiance to flux conversion will be location dependent. Because the longwave radiance to flux is based on a best fit regression for each view angle to simulations for a range of scenes the error at a given view angle will vary with scene. In addition to the fit error, errors from the modelling introduce further errors in the radiance to flux conversion. For instance, the plane parallel assumption results in fluxes exhibiting a low bias approaching 5% for the largest view angles, which corresponds to the edge of the GERB valid field of view. A 1-2% high bias is also known to exist for hot desert scenes for small viewing zenith angles (e.g. over the Sahara during the middle of the day) due to the limitations of the longwave radiance to flux conversion.

6. Instrument Overview

The GERB instruments are broadband radiometers making measurements of the TOA outgoing radiation from the Earth over the wavelength range from 0.32 μm to $>100 \mu\text{m}$. The instruments are mounted on the MSG satellites which are spin-stabilised, and comprise of an optical and electronic unit. The optical unit contains the imaging optics and detector system, a despin mirror, quartz filter and two onboard calibration sources (visible and thermal). The electronics unit controls the optical unit and provides data handling. The detectors are arranged in a linear array of 256-pixels oriented

north-south. The despun mirror is used to freeze the Earth view momentarily onto the detector array, adjusting the Earth's location by one pixel width for each rotation, enabling a full image to be built up over a period of approximately three minutes. The quartz filter is used to remove the infra-red component (4.0 μm to $>100 \mu\text{m}$) of the total incident radiation, thus providing a measure of only the shortwave (0.32 μm to 4.0 μm) component. The longwave component is derived by subtraction of the shortwave radiation component from the total radiation. The onboard calibration sources are used to monitor the performance and maintain knowledge of the instrument's calibration. A detailed description of the GERB instrument is provided in Harries *et al.* (2005).

7. References

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8. Dataset and Document Revision History

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